

Partners in crime

Nexus ed developers as co-leads

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This presentation explored the integration of Nexus educational developers as co-leads in educational projects within the Faculty of Medicine & Health at the University of New South Wales. It looked at their role in enhancing collaboration, fostering innovation, and driving impactful outcomes in medicine and health education.

Our aim was for participants to gain insights into the value of Nexus educational developers as co-leads and practical strategies for fostering innovation in their own projects within their own educational contexts in the faculty.

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